
EXTERNAL INFLUENCES AND ECOWAS ABILITY TO ADDRESS POLITICAL INSTABILITY: A STUDY OF NIGER REPUBLIC COUP

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Abstract

The July 26, 2023 military coup, executed by high-ranking officers of the Conseil National Pour la Sauvegarde de la Patrie (CNSP) led by General Abdourahamane Tchiani, has significantly impacted the country's political environment and the ECOWAS sub-region in general. This event, which ousted President Mohamed Bazoum, has raised critical questions about the influence of external factors and the efficacy of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) in managing political instability in view of the recurring military coups in the West African sub-region in recent times. Given this, the study examined how external actors contributed to the military coup in Niger Republic and the efficacy of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) in addressing it. Adopting Conflict Theory, primarily developed by Karl Marx, the research focuses on the inherent conflicts driven by competition for limited resources and power struggles. The study employs an explanatory research design to analyse the problematic. Data was analysed using the documentary method, which includes examining official reports, policy documents, and media articles to gather comprehensive information on external actors' involvement and ECOWAS's interventions. Textual analysis is used to interpret these documents, uncovering narratives and framing strategies utilized by different stakeholders. Based on the findings of the study, it recommends among others; ECOWAS and Western allies should prioritize diplomatic engagement with Niger's new leadership and local stakeholders to address underlying grievances, reduce anti-foreign sentiments, and foster inclusive governance moreso, the need for democratic governments within the West African political bloc to strengthen regional collaboration by involving all ECOWAS members in dialogue and decision-making processes to ensure a unified and effective response to political instability, balancing sanctions with support for humanitarian needs

Keywords: Coup, External Influence, ECOWAS, Political Instability, Niger Republic

Introduction

The political instability in Niger Republic, exemplified by the military coup on July 26, 2023, raises significant concerns about the influence of external actors and the efficacy of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) in maintaining democratic governance and stability. The coup, led by General Abdourahamane Tchiani, highlighted longstanding issues within Niger's political landscape, including security challenges and inadequate economic and social governance (Tschörner, 2023). Despite prior democratic progress, such as the election of President Mohamed Bazoum in 2021, the sudden military intervention underscored the fragility of Niger's democratic institutions, the entire Sahel region, and West Africa sub-region (Zambakari, 2023). The international response, particularly from the US, EU, and UN, as well as regional threats from ECOWAS, reflects the broader geopolitical implications of Niger's instability (Ajala, 2023).

The implications of the military coup on the socio-economic and political stability of Niger Republic and the ECOWAS sub-region are profound; Niger, despite its rich natural resources like uranium, ranks among the world's poorest countries according to the UN Human Development Index (2022). Tschörner (2023) pointed out that the lack of legitimacy and effective governance has exacerbated the security crisis, making the country an anchor of instability in the Sahel. The coup not only threatens Niger's socio-economic development but also destabilizes the broader region, affecting migration patterns, security cooperation, and economic partnerships. The international community's response, including sanctions and potential military interventions aimed to force out military leadership in Niger to pave way for democratic governance, has the potential to worsen humanitarian concerns and impede counter-terrorism efforts which further complicate governance and security challenges already faced in the West African sub-region (Ferragamo, 2023). It is against this backdrop, that this study seeks to examine the possible external influence responsible for the political instability in Niger.

In addition, ECOWAS's ability to effectively address political instability in Niger is called into question by this recent coup. Historically, domestic political crises have often led to military interventions in Niger, with the recent event reflecting a pattern of recurring instability despite ECOWAS's efforts (Tschörner, 2023). Additionally, the socio-economic impacts of the coup, considering Niger's ranking as one of the world's poorest countries despite its resource wealth (UN Human Development Index, 2022), underscore the profound challenges faced by both Niger and the broader ECOWAS sub-region.

Conceptualisation of Key Variables

External Influence

The concept of external influence within the context of a state, has attracted diverse scholarly opinions and interpretation. To offer a basic understanding of external influence, Quora (2024) refer to it as factors originating outside of an individual, organization, or system that exert an impact on them. These influences encompass a wide range, such as economic conditions, political shifts, technological advancements, social trends, competitive dynamics, market forces, legal frameworks, cultural norms, and environmental considerations. They significantly affect decision-making processes, behaviours, and outcomes by presenting opportunities or threats that necessitate strategic adjustments or policy changes. It is different from internal influence which emanate from within an entity itself, encompassing factors like values, beliefs, attitudes, motivations, goals, skills, knowledge, organizational culture, structure, resources, leadership styles, and operational processes which influence the overall performance of individuals, organizations, or systems.

According to Muscalu, Iancu, and Halmaghi (2016), external influence is reciprocal and involves interactions between an organization and its external environment, comprising institutions and forces that shape the organization's survival and development. These external forces directly or indirectly affect an organization's objectives, plans, procedures, activities, and outcomes, thereby exerting significant influence on internal dynamics and stresses within the organization's structure. In essence, external influence manifests as external factors acting upon an entity, altering its internal conditions and outcomes.

Within the context of state and its political and socioeconomic governance, external influence could encompass factors originating outside a nation that impact its internal dynamics, including foreign policies of other countries, international trade agreements, and global economic trends. For Ogele and Adamu (2021), it is the impact or effect originating from outside individuals, organizations, or nations, which can be either positive or negative and affects productivity. The authors argue that external influences significantly affect regional integration in West Africa, both positively and negatively. They highlight that entities like the United Nations and nonviolent state actors have played constructive roles in promoting integration across Africa, including support from foreign governments such as China. However, they criticize the role of France, noting that despite granting political independence to Francophone West African countries, France maintains strong control over their economies, particularly through the UMOA monetary policy. This has created divisions within ECOWAS regarding the adoption of a common currency, ECO, with Francophone countries pushing ahead independently. The authors suggest that ECOWAS should carefully evaluate external assistance to avoid compromising its self-reliance, and urge Francophone countries to reconsider their monetary union with France in favour of a more independent and regionally integrated approach akin to the European Union's currency system pre-Euro, which could expedite the implementation of the ECO within ECOWAS.

Furthermore, Obe (2023) reveals the profound external influences shaping Africa's economic landscape, particularly exacerbated by concurrent global events such as the Russian invasion of Ukraine. These external shocks, including adverse weather conditions and geopolitical tensions, have intensified inflation rates and borrowing costs across the continent. The author argues that external influence encompasses not only economic impacts like commodity price hikes and inflation spikes in food and energy sectors but also geopolitical manoeuvres by major powers vying for strategic resources and influence in Africa. This includes initiatives like China's Belt and Road Initiative and the broader geopolitical strategies of powers like Russia, the US, and the EU, which have direct implications on African stability and development trajectories.

Brenya and Adu-Gyamfi (2015) argue that Africa has faced four significant stages of external influence over the past five hundred years, each with detrimental impacts on the continent's development. These stages include slavery, where Africans were exploited by global traders; colonialism, which reshaped African societies and resources to serve European interests; neo-colonialism, characterized by external economic and political pressures; and globalization, which ties African economies to global trade and financial systems. The authors highlight that while modernization theory suggests Africa must mimic the developed world to progress, this ignores Africa's unique context. Dependency theory, on the other hand, points to Africa's ongoing reliance on the West as a root cause of its poverty, a situation the West perpetuates to maintain economic dominance. Although these external forces are significant, the authors also acknowledge that Africa's internal dynamics contribute to its challenges (Brenya & Adu-Gyamfi, 2015).

In the area of foreign policy, Gimba and Ibrahim (2018), argue that the profound impact of international organizations on is seen in state behaviour and foreign policy. They argue that institutions like the United Nations play crucial roles in modifying state actions and acting independently, ensuring no state can pursue policies that harm others. The authors highlight the influence of world public opinion, alliances, and international treaties in shaping foreign policy, citing historical and contemporary examples. They underscore the interconnectedness of these factors, asserting that a state's geopolitical location, multinational corporations, and liberation movements also significantly determine its foreign policy. Hence, understanding foreign policy requires a holistic analysis of these intertwined external influences.

Lastly, Dickson (2017) is of the view that external influence which stems from the broader international system rather than the state's internal characteristics, shape a state's foreign policy. Drawing on Neack (2008), Dickson underscores that foreign policy is largely a function of a state's position within the global hierarchy, which is dictated by power dynamics and state-to-state relations at bilateral, multilateral, regional, and global levels. Neoclassical realists like Rose (1998) argue that a state's foreign policy is ultimately constrained by the international environment, with power capabilities—such as military strength, economic size, and geographic location—delineating a state's foreign policy options. Dickson also highlights that the prevalent international power structure, whether unipolar, bipolar, tripolar, or multipolar, significantly impacts foreign policy decisions, as seen during the Cold War and post-Cold War eras. Additionally, the concepts of anarchy, international norms, globalization, and membership in international organizations and alliances further influence a state's foreign policy by encouraging certain behaviours and restricting others.

Political Instability

In academic literature, there is no universally accepted conceptual definition of political instability, as scholars' opinion is influenced by different realities. Jannils (2021) defines political instability as closely linked with instability in policies or institutions, which is particularly relevant for economists studying the impacts of different economic policies. The author argues that significant policy and institutional shifts often arise from changes in political regimes, such as the transition from authoritarianism to democracy in Eastern Europe, which moved from centrally planned to market economies. Jannils further state that political regime instability can result in abrupt changes in economic policies, especially when governments with opposing ideologies replace each other. Additionally, mass civil protests, whether peaceful or violent, can force governments to adjust or abandon policies. This uncertainty about future economic policies and institutional changes Jannils opines that it profoundly affects economic agents, making it a crucial area of interest for economic research.

Dirks and Schmidt (2023) sees political instability as the extent to which the distribution of power within a political system is challenged by internal or external actors. The authors distinguished political instability from political uncertainty, which refers to the uncertainty arising from potential changes in the political situation and their uncertain impacts. While political instability can lead to policy uncertainty, a high level of policy uncertainty does not necessarily result in political instability. Supporting with practical example, Dirks and Schmidt state that although policy uncertainty increased in advanced economies during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, political instability remained relatively stable. This suggests that while policy uncertainty and political instability can be related, they are not always directly correlated.

Furthermore, Hartwell (2018a, 2018b) defines political instability as the volatility of policies or the instability within and between political and economic institutions. This definition emphasizes how frequent and unpredictable changes in policies or institutional frameworks can disrupt governance and economic functioning. In contrast, Jong-A-Pin (2009) approaches political instability from a different angle, identifying it through four distinct dimensions: politically motivated violence, mass civil protests, instability within the political regime, and instability of the political regime itself. While Hartwell focuses on the fluidity and unpredictability of institutional and policy environments as key indicators of instability, Jong-A-Pin provides a more granular breakdown of instability by considering both the nature of political violence and the internal and external pressures faced by political regimes. This distinction highlights the complexity of political instability, reflecting ongoing debates among scholars about its precise nature and measurement.

In Howell's (2011) perspective, political instability is primarily attributed to diminishing government unity, legislative effectiveness, and public support. Howell emphasizes that as these core components of governance weaken, political systems become more unstable. This view is supported by Hadjar and Kothemann (2014), who note a decline in trust toward political institutions in advanced economies since the 1980s. Their research indicates that this trend is evident in liberal democracies, where the increasing strain on political institutions exacerbates instability. They argue that the causes of this instability are complex and multifaceted, involving a broad range of social and economic factors.

Extending the conceptual analysis of political instability, Diamond (2015) attributes the pressure on Western democracies to poor governance. He cites specific examples such as the 2013 U.S. federal government shutdown and legislative gridlock as manifestations of governmental inefficacy. Furthermore, Diamond highlights the role of rising mass protests, driven by economic stagnation, austerity measures, rising inequality, and other crises. This broader spectrum of factors, including anti-migration sentiment and populist movements in Europe, underscores the intricate interplay between political instability and socio-economic discontent, as documented by Cross-National Time-Series Data Archive (CNTS).

From an economic perspective, political instability has notable impacts on both investment and consumption behaviours. Asteriou and Price (2001) suggest that instability creates uncertainty, leading investors to delay decisions and consequently causing a decline in investment. Similarly, risk-averse consumers may increase savings and reduce expenditures during periods of instability, as indicated by Bahmani-Oskooee and Maki Nayeri (2020). This cautious behaviour extends to durable goods purchases and mirrors investor attitudes. The relationship between political instability and government consumption is less straightforward. While Darby et al. (2004) argue that instability may prompt increased short-term government spending, Ponticelli and Voth (2020) provide evidence that fiscal retrenchment, particularly expenditure cuts, can exacerbate political unrest, illustrating a reciprocal relationship between government spending and political stability. From the foregoing, political instability refers to a situation where the political system is characterized by frequent changes, uncertainty, and lack of continuity. It often involves weakened government authority, legislative gridlock, declining public trust, and increased social unrest. These conditions can lead to disruptions in governance and affect economic and social stability.

Coup d'état

Different conceptual clarifications of coup d'état exist in academic literature. Marsteintredet, and Malamud (2019) define a coup d'état as a sudden and often military-supported removal

of a government, which is traditionally seen as a severe threat to democratic stability. This abrupt seizure of power typically signals the collapse of democratic institutions and the end of the democratic regime. Their further analysis underscores that coups d'état not only disrupt the existing political order but also pose significant challenges to democratic resilience and continuity, emphasizing their historical role as a major destabilizing force in democratic societies.

According to the Mo Ibrahim Foundation (2023), coup d'état, commonly referred to as a coup, is the sudden, often violent or illegal seizure of political power or government control by a group, usually within the military or other influential factions. These coups are marked by a highly organized and centralized effort aimed at displacing the existing government and replacing it with a new ruling authority, frequently comprised of the coup leaders themselves. This act can disrupt constitutional order and may manifest in various forms, including military, civilian, political, or hybrid coups. The motivations behind such coups can be diverse, encompassing political grievances, power struggles, or ideological and social factors. The Foundation's view underscores the multifaceted nature of coups and highlights the range of actors and reasons involved in such upheavals.

Furthermore, Encyclopaedia Britannica (2024), defined coup d'état as the sudden, violent overthrow of an existing government by a small group, typically involving control over the armed forces, police, or other military elements. Unlike revolutions, which involve widespread public participation and aim to achieve comprehensive social, economic, or political change, coups primarily result in a rapid change in leadership without substantial modifications to the nation's fundamental policies or power structures. The Britannica notes that historical examples of modern coups include Napoleon Bonaparte's overthrow of the Directory on November 9, 1799 (18 Brumaire) and Louis Napoleon's dissolution of the French Second Republic's assembly in 1851. This perspective emphasizes that while coups are dramatic shifts in governance, they often leave the broader socio-economic landscape largely intact.

According to Pryce and Time (2023), a coup d'état is described as an unauthorized takeover of power, where military or rebellious forces forcibly replace existing authorities and suspend legal norms. They liken a coup to an invasion of a town by soldiers who arrest officials without due process, disrupting the established order and using violence to impose their rule. This type of regime change is characterized by a lack of legitimacy and a tendency to impose control through terror, undermining democratic principles and societal stability. The authors emphasize that coups often stem from dissatisfaction with the current government, which might be driven by its failure to address economic and political grievances. However, despite the rhetoric of reform or improvement, coups frequently perpetuate instability rather than resolve underlying issues.

Pryce and Time (2023) further argue that coups, particularly in African contexts, often arise in settings with weak political and institutional frameworks. They highlight that economic hardships and political instability can serve as catalysts for such upheavals. Although military regimes promise to rectify governmental failures, the authors note that these regimes rarely improve the nation's economic conditions. Instead, coups often lead to international isolation and reduced financial support from Western and regional entities, exacerbating the socio-economic challenges faced by the country. The authors advocate for a deeper exploration of the causes and consequences of coups and suggest that understanding these dynamics is

crucial for developing effective measures to prevent such occurrences and promote stable governance in Africa.

In the perspective of Varo (2012), a coup d'état is specifically an event where a segment of the military seizes control of the state's apex, displacing the current regime and commanding the state's operations from that point. This definition distinctly separates coups from other forms of regime change, such as revolutions, where non-military actors play a pivotal role. Varo emphasizes that his definition does not cover scenarios where the military merely refrains from suppressing popular opposition or permits a civilian-led democratic transition, as these situations fall outside the traditional understanding of a coup d'état.

Varo differentiates between two primary categories of coups d'état: non-democratic and democratic. Non-democratic coups involve the military replacing existing political leaders with its own members, thereby maintaining the existing government structure but under military control. Such coups often lead to authoritarian rule, as exemplified by recent events like Gaddafi's overthrow in Libya and al-Bashir's coup in Sudan. In contrast, democratic coups are characterized by their aim to dismantle authoritarian or totalitarian regimes in favor of democratic reforms. These coups are marked by the military's facilitation of free and fair elections and a subsequent transfer of power to democratically elected leaders, though Varo notes that these coups are inherently undemocratic due to their reliance on military force.

Varo's framework for understanding democratic coups presents a nuanced view, acknowledging that while coups are inherently non-democratic, some can be more conducive to democratic outcomes than others. He outlines seven attributes that define a democratic coup, including a response to popular uprisings, the establishment of free elections, and the transfer of power to elected officials. Despite these attributes, Varo cautions that democratic coups are exceptions rather than the rule, and he does not claim that such coups are preferable to other democratic transition methods. His analysis underscores the complex and context-dependent nature of military interventions in political transitions, rejecting simplistic categorizations in favor of a more detailed examination of their outcomes and implications.

Review of Related Literature

The review of relevant literature for this study was thematically carried out and covers the follows:

- i. External Dimension of Political Instability in Niger Republic
- ii. ECOWAS Response to Political Instability in Niger Republic
- iii. Socio-economic Implications of the Political Instability in Niger Republic

External Dimension of Political Instability in Niger Republic

The surge in military takeover of democracies within the West African sub-region in recent years continue to attract the attention of not only governments and international organisations, but have further fuelled academic inquiry among scholars into the possible triggers of such political instability, especially with the Sahel country of Niger. While this study takes a deep look into scholarly perspectives that have made efforts to establish the link between the activities of certain external forces and the recent political instability in Niger, there is no doubt that the major cause of the political conflict in Niger is the failure of democratic leadership. Salihu, Doke, & Aning (2023) argued that the crisis of governance in

Africa has significantly destabilized the region, leading to a surge in political violence, intra-state conflicts, and necessitating peacekeeping missions. They identify governance deficits, underdevelopment, social cleavages, poverty, and economic issues as the root causes fuelling these political crises. In particular, violent extremism and the failure of governments to manage rising violence have prompted military interventions in countries such as Mali, Burkina Faso, Guinea, and Niger, where coup leaders justify their actions by citing inadequate counter-terrorism efforts. Despite initial support from civilians, these military coups have not resolved governance issues and have often exacerbated extremist violence. The authors highlight that civil-military relations remain fragile due to historical colonial and post-independence experiences, with many militaries resisting reforms and lacking proper oversight, leading to politicized and corrupt defence officials. This fragility is particularly evident in Francophone West Africa, where a resurgence of coups is closely tied to growing anti-French sentiments, fuelled by perceptions of neo-colonialist and exploitative policies, resulting in widespread popular protests and attacks on French interests.

Furthermore, Salihu, Doke, & Aning (2023) examining the external dimension of the political instability in Niger emphasized the strategic importance of Niger to Western allies, especially France, in combating terrorism in the Sahel region. According to the authors, under President Bazoum's government, Niger became a crucial partner for the West as relations with neighbouring Mali and Burkina Faso deteriorated. Niger hosts military bases from France, the US, and Germany, and benefits from substantial military aid and training support, which is vital for France's geopolitical interests by containing the expansion of terrorist groups. Salihu *et al.* maintained that the West has heavily invested in Niger's security and development, with significant financial assistance from the EU and the US, and military presence. Furthermore, the author stressed that Niger's natural resources, such as uranium and the Trans-Saharan gas pipeline, highlight its strategic value. However, the recent coup in Niger, driven by military dissatisfaction with the foreign presence and anti-French sentiment, poses significant challenges to regional stability, strains diplomatic relations with France, and raises questions about the effectiveness of foreign intervention. Additionally, the growing influence of Russia in Africa, particularly through the Wagner Group, further complicates the geopolitical landscape in Niger and the broader Sahel region.

Again, Zambakari (2023) provided a comprehensive analysis of the intricate political landscape of Niger, emphasizing the enduring impact of French colonialism and the role of international interventions. The author affirmed that Niger, as a former French colony, inherited a centralized power structure that has persisted since its independence in 1960. This legacy Zambakari argued has fostered economic disparities and political discontent, with French influence notably marked by the exploitation of Niger's uranium resources. The author stressed that the concentration of power among a small elite has historically marginalized large segments of the population, leading to periodic political instability and military coups. These coups often highlight issues such as deteriorating security and poor economic management, reflecting the broader governance challenges rooted in the historical legacies of colonial rule and resource exploitation.

Additionally, Zambakari (2023) pointed out that Niger's strategic location in the Sahel region made it a focal point for US military aid aimed at countering terrorism in post-9/11. While this aid bolstered Niger's security forces, it also inadvertently empowered a cadre of US-trained officers who have been involved in multiple coups across West Africa. This paradox the author stressed underscores the unintended consequences of security assistance, where efforts to enhance stability have sometimes contributed to political instability. Furthermore,

Zambakari noted that the role of international actors, particularly the US and France, is critical in examining the unrest in Niger. While these powers have a vested interest in maintaining stability and combating terrorism, their influence has sometimes inadvertently exacerbated tensions and divisions, evident in the involvement of US-trained officers in coups. This highlights the complexities of foreign military interventions and their contribution to the political unrest in African countries.

According to the International Institute for Strategic Studies (2023), the recent coup in Niger underscores escalating security challenges and internal power conflicts, reflecting a pattern of military coups in the region since 2019. This trend, which indicated diminishing Western influence and increasing Russian involvement, began with Sudan's coup in 2019 and now includes a contiguous bloc of military regimes extending from the Atlantic Ocean to the Red Sea. Despite resistance from countries such as Benin and Ghana, which have successfully thwarted similar interventions, the general pattern highlights the decline of Western influence and the failure of multilateral efforts to stabilize the political and security landscape in the Sahelian belt.

Demuyneck and Böhm (2023) analysed the recent military coup in Niger, which marks a significant setback for a nation once considered a democratic beacon in the Sahel. According to the authors, under President Mohamed Bazoum, Niger had bolstered its alliances with Western countries, securing considerable international support in terms of financial aid and military cooperation from the EU, US, and France, and positioning itself as a key player in regional security against extremism and Russian influence. Despite these efforts, Niger's stability was perpetually undermined by deep-rooted issues such as poverty, weak governance, and persistent security threats from violent extremism. The authors highlight that the coup, the fifth since Niger gained independence, reveals profound internal divisions and power struggles within its military and political realms. Public dissatisfaction continued to simmer under Bazoum's leadership, driven by unfulfilled expectations and resentment towards foreign military presence, as evidenced by protests against French forces and allegations of imperialism. This discontent, combined with economic difficulties and perceived inefficiencies in counterterrorism, created a volatile environment, ultimately leading to the recent political upheaval. The situation casts uncertainty over Niger's future amid the ongoing regional challenges.

Otte (2023) examined the aftermath of the recent coup in Niger, emphasizing the severe strain on relations with France and the broader implications for regional stability in the Sahel. Following the military takeover, the new junta renounced critical security cooperation agreements with France, leading to a rapid decline in diplomatic relations. This action prompted protests at the French embassy, necessitating the emergency evacuation of French citizens and disrupting French media in Niger. Otte argued that the coup endangered ongoing anti-jihadist efforts reliant on international military support and posed significant threats to Western strategic and economic interests, particularly given Niger's importance to France as a major uranium supplier. The coup also highlighted shifting global influence dynamics, as Russia capitalized on the situation to expand its presence in the region through private military contractors. Otte underscored that the evolving situation in the Sahel had far-reaching implications, affecting not only regional security but also global power balances and humanitarian issues.

ECOWAS Response to Political Instability in Niger Republic

In their respective analyses, Tschörner (2023) and Ajala (2023) both provided comprehensive insights into the political crisis in Niger following the military coup in July 2023. Tschörner (2023) observed that the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) deviated from its typical protocol of suspension and transitional negotiations by imposing severe economic sanctions and threatening military intervention unless President Bazoum was reinstated within a week. Western allies such as France, Germany, the EU, and the US supported these measures, suspending aid and security cooperation and evacuating their nationals. Tschörner further noted that the situation exacerbated tensions between France and Niger's military junta, with the threat of external intervention ultimately consolidating the junta's power. Internal opposition within ECOWAS, notably from Nigeria and Togo, advocated for diplomatic solutions, while Algeria's proposal for a transitional period was rejected by the junta. This coup strained Niger's relations with its Western partners and risked aligning the country more closely with authoritarian regimes like Russia and China, complicating regional stabilization efforts.

Ajala (2023) detailed the immediate actions taken by ECOWAS at an emergency meeting in Abuja, Nigeria, on 30 July. The regional bloc demanded the immediate release and reinstatement of the detained President Bazoum, who had been held by the military since 19 July, issuing a one-week ultimatum to the Nigerien military. Ajala highlighted that General Abdourahamane Tchiani, head of Niger's presidential guard, declared himself the new head of state on 28 July, following the coup. Despite the military leaders' warnings against regional and foreign interventions, they did not provide a clear plan for the country's future. Ajala's account underscored the urgency and severity of ECOWAS's response, reflecting the regional bloc's determination to restore constitutional order in Niger through all necessary measures, including potential use of force.

In the aftermath of the coup in Niger, Ogbulia (2023) detailed how both regional and international bodies, including the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and the African Union (AU), swiftly denounced the military takeover. Ogbulia highlighted that these organizations, along with global actors such as the US and the EU, voiced significant concerns over the coup's implications for political stability in the Sahel and the broader West African region. The author emphasized that ECOWAS and other international actors explored a range of punitive measures, including sanctions, suspension from regional organizations, and the cessation of financial aid, all contingent upon successful diplomatic negotiations. Ogbulia also pointed out that while there was a unified global condemnation of the coup, the real challenge lay in bridging the gap between condemnation and effective action, with a focus on both restoring constitutional order through mediation and addressing the underlying socio-economic issues that contributed to the coup.

The International Crisis Group (2023) analyzed the aftermath of the coup in Niamey, highlighting its detrimental impact on regional cooperation. According to their findings, Niger's neighbors and Western partners adopted stringent measures against the junta, driven by security concerns and fears of a coup contagion. ECOWAS imposed severe sanctions and threatened military intervention to reinstate President Bazoum, although such action seemed improbable without Nigeria's involvement. Experts widely agreed that military intervention would lead to disastrous consequences, including civilian casualties and increased regional instability. Mali and Burkina Faso's pledges of mutual defense for Niger's junta were deemed uncertain in their capacity to provide meaningful support. ECOWAS sanctions have

worsened Niger's already severe food insecurity and disrupted critical imports and services, while the EU's financial support freeze compounded the crisis. The junta's blockade of humanitarian aid and restrictions on international NGOs have further aggravated the situation. For stable cooperation, the report suggested that the EU and ECOWAS should prioritize a civilian-led transition and exhibit flexibility in engaging with the new authorities.

Melly (2023) provided a detailed examination of the Niger coup, emphasizing the junta's refusal to engage with ECOWAS, the AU, or the UN, which resulted in heavy economic sanctions and threats of military intervention from ECOWAS aimed at restoring President Bazoum. These sanctions led to rising food prices and power disruptions, jeopardizing regional democratic stability after six coups in less than three years. Unlike previous coups in Mali, Guinea, and Burkina Faso, which had structural motivations, Niger's coup was portrayed as a narrow power grab by elite military leaders, threatening development and security progress. Melly noted that this trend posed a broader ideological challenge to the ECOWAS model of civilian-led governance, amid growing disenchantment with traditional politics and resentment towards France. The emergence of Russian flags in Niamey was seen as a reflection of complex social dynamics rather than direct Russian influence. The report suggested that ECOWAS must carefully navigate these challenges, as sanctions alone might strengthen the junta's position, making diplomacy and political engagement essential for addressing democratic erosion in West Africa.

According to Otte (2023), the Niger military coup against President Mohamed Bazoum's democratically elected government instigated a regional crisis in Central Africa, drawing swift condemnation and threats of military intervention from ECOWAS aimed at restoring democratic governance. Despite ECOWAS' ultimatum passing without compliance from the junta led by Gen. Abdourahmane Tchiani, neighbouring states such as Mali and Burkina Faso aligned themselves with the junta's defiance, warning of potential regional conflict if ECOWAS pursued military intervention. Niger's closure of airspace further underscored the severity of the standoff, marking a critical test for regional stability and the credibility of African governance bodies like ECOWAS. Otte's analysis emphasized the junta's consolidation of power and defiance in the face of international pressure, highlighting the complex dynamics of regional alliances and the junta's strategic manoeuvring against external intervention. The situation in Niger thus posed profound challenges not only to regional stability but also to the efficacy of regional organizations like ECOWAS in enforcing democratic norms and governance standards across member states amidst escalating geopolitical tensions.

Lastly, Salihu, Doke, and Aning's (2023) assessment of ECOWAS's response to the Niger coup highlighted a robust but contentious approach by the regional body. According to the authors, ECOWAS swift condemnation of the coup and initiation of sanctions, including suspension of Niger's membership and financial restrictions, demonstrated a commitment to its democracy and governance frameworks. However, Nigeria's additional measures, such as cutting electricity and closing borders, exacerbated conditions for ordinary Nigeriens without yielding compliance from the junta. Salihu *et al.* affirmed that Niger military junta's defiance and garnering of support despite sanctions underscored criticisms of ECOWAS's perceived inconsistency in dealing with coups across member states, raising questions about the efficacy and influence of external powers in the region. The threat of military intervention exacerbated fears of a potential proxy conflict, particularly with backing from neighbouring military regimes and potential involvement from international actors like Russia and Western powers, further complicating the regional stability landscape.

Socio-economic Implications of the Political Instability in Niger Republic

The current political instability in Niger Republic occasioned by the military usurpation of civilian leadership in 2023, is not without significant consequences for the country's development as different scholars have explored. In Tschörner's (2023) analysis of the military coup in Niger, the author highlighted its profound impact on the pro-democracy movement in the Sahel region. The ousting of President Bazoum and subsequent strong military and popular support for the new regime have diminished prospects for his reinstatement. Drawing on historical precedents, Tschörner argued that military regimes reliant on populist rhetoric often face internal instability and external challenges. The detention of former President Issoufou and contentious moves by the junta have strained alliances within the CNSP and exacerbated societal tensions, particularly along ethnic and identity lines. Furthermore, Niger's foreign policy shift towards Russia adds another layer of complexity, potentially causing rifts within the junta and among international partners. To mitigate these risks, Tschörner emphasizes the necessity of inclusive negotiations involving national and regional stakeholders, though acknowledging the considerable complexities and risks associated with Germany's potential policy responses.

Similarly, Ajala (2023) emphasised the significant consequences of Niger's recent coup on regional stability and international relations. As a pivotal ally in Western efforts against insurgency and illegal migration, Niger's political upheaval jeopardizes ongoing security initiatives in the Sahel. Ajala suggests that the new military leadership might exploit these challenges to garner international legitimacy, possibly aligning with entities like the Wagner group, thereby enhancing Russian influence in the region. The coup represents a setback for democratic governance in Africa, with neighbouring countries considering a collective military response to regional insecurity. Ajala stresses the imperative for African leaders to reaffirm their commitment to democratic principles amidst these unsettling trends, emphasizing the need for sustained regional stability and cooperation. Both Tschörner (2023) and Ajala (2023) agreed on the critical nature of inclusive dialogue and strategic international engagement to stabilize Niger and the broader Sahel region, while recognizing the intricate geopolitical dynamics at play and the imperative for nuanced policy responses from key global actors.

Focused on the uncertain future of Niger following the coup, Yabi (2023) expressed concerns over the historical pattern of military rulers entrenching themselves in power rather than facilitating a transition to a fairer political system. According to the author, the coup disrupted Niger's economic progress and educational reforms, posing significant challenges for the Sahel region, West Africa, and ECOWAS. Yabi noted that the junta's radical stance complicated dialogue efforts and cautioned against external military intervention, particularly opposed by neighbours like Algeria. He highlighted the difficult decisions faced by France and the United States regarding their military presence in Niger, with the U.S. having more diplomatic flexibility. Yabi underscored the importance of preventing the coup leaders from monopolizing power and fostering political compromise through inclusive dialogue among key actors in Niger, suggesting that American diplomacy could support regional stabilization initiatives.

Lastly, Ferragamo (2023) discussed the trend towards military rule in Niger, highlighting significant regional and international concerns. The author affirmed that observers feared this shift could exacerbate instability in West Africa, undermine efforts against extremist groups, and potentially increase migration flows. Again, Ferragamo stressed that the expulsion of

French forces from Burkina Faso and Mali had already resulted in heightened violence in those regions, complicating security dynamics further. Additionally, Ferragamo noted that the breakdown in democratic governance threatened partnerships, such as US-Niger relations, potentially allowing Russia to expand its influence as an alternative partner. With Niger's strategic resources, particularly uranium, the author argued that Moscow saw an opportunity to enhance its presence in resource-rich African nations. The situation broader concerns about regional stability and international geopolitical dynamics, impacting security, migration, and global power relations in Africa.

Gap in Knowledge

Existing literature primarily focuses on ECOWAS' roles and mechanisms in addressing political crises within member states but lacks comprehensive analysis of how external powers' interventions and strategic interests intersect with ECOWAS initiatives. Specifically, there is a need to explore how these external influences shape ECOWAS' effectiveness in mediating political disputes and restoring democratic governance in Niger, considering the geopolitical competition and resource interests in the region. Additionally, there is limited research on the impact of these dynamics on regional stability and the ability of ECOWAS to maintain cohesion and implement effective crisis management strategies in the face of external pressures and interventions.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts Conflict Theory. Conflict theory was primarily developed by Karl Marx, a 19th-century philosopher, economist, and sociologist, who is considered the founding figure of this theoretical perspective. Marx formulated the foundational ideas of conflict theory in his works such as "The Communist Manifesto" (1848) and "Das Kapital" (1867). He argued that society is in a state of perpetual conflict due to competition for limited resources. Later, other sociologists like Max Weber (1922) and Ralf Dahrendorf (1959) expanded upon Marx's ideas, incorporating additional dimensions such as status and authority into the analysis of social conflicts (Ritzer, 2008).

The fundamental principles of conflict theory were laid out by Marx in the mid-19th century, with "The Communist Manifesto" being one of the earliest publications in 1848, and "Das Kapital" following in 1867. These works laid the groundwork for understanding social and economic inequalities. In the 20th century, Weber's "Economy and Society" (1922) and Dahrendorf's "Class and Class Conflict in Industrial Society" (1959) were significant contributions that further developed and diversified conflict theory (Coser, 1956).

The core tenet of conflict theory is that society is composed of groups with conflicting interests, primarily between those who control resources and those who do not. Marx posited that societal conflict arises from the inherent inequalities in the capitalist system, where the bourgeoisie (capitalist class) exploit the proletariat (working class) for economic gain. This exploitation leads to class struggles, which are the driving force behind social change. Weber added that social conflict could also arise from struggles over power and prestige, not just economic resources. Dahrendorf emphasized that authority and power differentials create inherent conflicts within society, even in ostensibly stable or democratic contexts (Marx & Engels, 1848; Weber, 1922; Dahrendorf, 1959).

Despite its influential insights, conflict theory has faced several criticisms. Critics argue that it overly emphasizes economic and class conflicts while neglecting other forms of social stratification, such as gender, race, and ethnicity. Additionally, conflict theory is often criticized for its deterministic view of social relations, implying that conflict is inevitable and omnipresent. Some sociologists believe it underestimates the role of consensus and social cohesion in maintaining societal order. Moreover, the theory's focus on macro-level analysis often overlooks the nuances of individual agency and micro-level interactions (Collins, 1994; Turner, 2005).

Application of Theory

From a conflict theory perspective, the coup in Niger can be seen as a manifestation of deeper socio-economic and political conflicts within the country. The ruling elite and military factions, representing different interests, are in conflict over control of the state's resources and governance. External influences, such as interventions by global powers like Russia and traditional allies like France, further complicate these conflicts. These external actors have their own strategic interests, particularly concerning Niger's rich uranium resources, and their involvement can exacerbate internal divisions and power struggles, undermining efforts by regional bodies like ECOWAS to stabilize the country (Marx & Engels, 1848).

Conflict theory also highlights how ECOWAS's ability to address political instability is affected by broader power structures and inequalities. ECOWAS operates within a context of unequal power relations both within its member states and in relation to external powers. The involvement of the US, EU, and UN, and the imposition of sanctions, reflect the global power dynamics influencing regional stability efforts. Moreover, ECOWAS's actions are constrained by the competing interests of powerful member states and the strategic calculations of external actors. This theoretical lens suggests that effective resolution of Niger's instability requires addressing the underlying structural inequalities and power imbalances, both within the country and in the broader geopolitical context (Dahrendorf, 1959; Weber, 1922). By understanding these dynamics, conflict theory provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing the challenges and limitations faced by ECOWAS in mediating political crises influenced by external factors.

External Influence and Political Instability In Niger Republic

The external dimension of political instability in Niger Republic underscores the significant influence of external actors on the country's political dynamics. Studies have highlighted how the Sahel region's strategic importance has attracted substantial Western military and financial support, aimed primarily at countering terrorism. Under President Bazoum, Niger became a crucial ally for France, the US, and other Western nations, hosting military bases and receiving extensive aid to combat extremist threats. However, the presence of foreign forces has also incited local resentment, contributing to anti-French sentiments and popular protests. This sentiment, compounded by the military's dissatisfaction with the foreign presence and the perception of neo-colonial exploitation, has been a driving force behind recent coups. The increased Russian influence in the region, notably through the Wagner Group, further complicates the geopolitical landscape, as Niger's instability reflects broader regional and international power struggles (Salihu, Doke, & Aning, 2023; Zambakari, 2023; International Institute for Strategic Studies, 2023).

ECOWAS's response to the political instability in Niger has been notably robust, diverging from its usual approach of negotiation and transitional arrangements by imposing severe economic sanctions and threatening military intervention. This strategy, supported by Western allies, underscores ECOWAS's determination to uphold democratic principles and regional stability. However, the impact of these sanctions has been profound, exacerbating Niger's already severe food insecurity and disrupting essential services. Additionally, the coup has strained Niger's relations with Western partners and heightened the risk of aligning more closely with authoritarian regimes like Russia and China. The divergent stances within ECOWAS, with some members advocating for diplomatic solutions, further highlight the complexities of achieving a unified regional response. The situation in Niger underscores the challenges of balancing punitive measures with effective diplomacy to restore constitutional order and stability in the region (Tschörner, 2023; Ajala, 2023; Ogbulia, 2023).

Findings

The study reveals that external actors significantly influence political instability in Niger. Western military and financial support, primarily aimed at combating terrorism, has made Niger a strategic ally under President Bazoum, leading to the establishment of foreign military bases. However, this foreign presence has incited local resentment and anti-French sentiments, fueling recent coups. Additionally, increased Russian influence, especially through the Wagner Group, complicates the geopolitical landscape. ECOWAS's unprecedented response to the instability, including severe economic sanctions and the threat of military intervention, underscores its commitment to regional stability but has exacerbated Niger's food insecurity and strained relations with Western allies.

Conclusion

The political instability in Niger highlights the complex interplay between local and international factors. While external support from Western nations aimed at combating terrorism has made Niger a critical ally, it has also contributed to local discontent and political upheaval. The growing influence of Russia further complicates the situation, reflecting broader regional and international power struggles. ECOWAS's robust response underscores the challenges of balancing punitive measures with diplomatic efforts to restore stability and uphold democratic principles. Effective resolution of Niger's instability requires nuanced strategies that address both internal grievances and external influences.

Recommendations:

1. ECOWAS and Western allies should prioritize diplomatic engagement with Niger's new leadership and local stakeholders to address underlying grievances, reduce anti-foreign sentiments, and foster inclusive governance.
2. To mitigate local resentment, Western nations should reassess their military strategies, emphasizing capacity-building and collaboration with local forces rather than maintaining a large foreign presence.
3. There is need for democratic governments within the West African political bloc to strengthen regional collaboration by involving all ECOWAS members in dialogue and decision-making processes to ensure a unified and effective response to political instability, balancing sanctions with support for humanitarian needs.

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